

CROSSING THE BORDERS IN UTILIZING ENGLISH VARIETIES: FILIPINO TEACHERS' EXPERIENCES AND PERCEPTIONS

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Crossing the Borders in Utilizing English Varieties: Filipino Teachers' Experiences and Perceptions

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Abstract

The success of teaching and learning English largely depends on language teachers. In addition to their technical and pedagogical expertise, the teachers' proficiency in several languages is crucial in ensuring that learners acquire English to the greatest extent possible. Filipino English teachers vary in terms of their experiences in teaching English in nations where it is used as a foreign language (EFL), English as a second language (ESL), or English as a native language (ENL), especially when it comes to using the English variety in the classroom. The study aims to determine Filipino teachers' teaching experiences and perceptions of using English varieties in teaching in the ENL/ESL/EFL countries. This qualitative study employs the case study design and follows Kachru's Three Concentric Circles Model. Three Filipino teachers were chosen as participants using purposive sampling were selected according to the following criteria: Filipino female teachers who are teaching English to middle/junior high school in ENL, ESL, and EFL countries only, ages ranged from 25-45, with Masters degree related to their field of teaching, and has taught English for more than two years. The research questionnaire, one-on-one interview, and focus-group discussion were used to collect relevant data about the study. The direct transcriptions from the audio recordings of the individual interviews were subjected to data processing using Creswell's Thematic Analysis. The study's findings showed that the use of different English varieties is intimately related to the linguistic society's dominant language and the primary teaching objectives. Although teachers consider American English the mainstream variation, it is evident that all three linguistic groups also utilize the local varieties of English. It also showed that their beliefs on using different forms of English in the classroom were primarily based on functionality, proximity, inclusivity and awareness, and propensity for comprehension.

Keywords: *English varieties, experiences and perceptions, Kachru's Three Concentric Circles Model*

Introduction

With English's linguistic landscape changing quickly and rising global demand, the modern world faces new challenges. English, the most widely spoken language worldwide in the twenty-first century, has grown in significance for cross-border communication and academic pursuits in science, information, technology, education, entertainment, and politics. Teaching English, known as English Language Teaching (ELT) or English Language Education (ELE), throughout the world is one element responsible for the extraordinary spread of the language. Salih and Holi (2018) hypothesized that a variety of factors, such as the use of English in education and the eventual quick growth of internationalization of English and education, are responsible for the language's rapid growth and spread as well as its rise in the international arena based on ELT perspectives. Given the present trend of increased demand for English, it is necessary to enhance ELT or ELE even among speakers of other languages.

For the sake of the language learners, schools worldwide work to ensure that the teachers hired to teach English demonstrate a particular degree of competency and fluency in the language and knowledge and pedagogical abilities in English language teaching. Vodopija-Krstanovic and Marinac (2019) stressed that, in teaching English as an international language, it is essential to consider what English teachers need to know and how they should be prepared to teach. Renandya et al. (2018) also stressed that all English language teachers need to have a reasonably high level of proficiency in English to carry out their teaching and to serve as models of competent users of English. Lee (2023) further asserted that the teaching of English now is more about gaining "the ability to shuttle between different varieties of English and different speech communities," where language users need to have an awareness of multiple English varieties, develop intercultural sensitivity to contexts and constraints, and possess interactive, and collaborative skills. It is then imperative to consider the linguistic competence of teachers in the hiring of language teachers, especially those who will be teaching in various language contexts where English is used as a Native language (ENL), English as a Second Language (ESL), or English as a Foreign language (EFL).

Countries around the globe have set guidelines for hiring English language teachers. Elyas and Alghofaili (2019) claim that Native English-speaking teachers (NESTs) are believed to be ideal language teachers, which is why language centers and even universities around the globe use this as the basis for the hiring of NESTs due to their teaching qualifications and experiences. However, the global spread of English and its increasing demand as an international language has increased the demand for English teachers, including Non-native English-speaking teachers (NNESTs). Floris and Renandya (2020) stipulate that the increasing demand led to the increase of non-native English-speaking teachers (NNESTs) significantly outnumbering the native English-speaking teachers (NESTs) where 80% of the 15 million English teachers worldwide (or over 12 million) are NNESTs. This includes all Filipino teachers, who are known for their exceptional communication skills in the English language since the Philippines is an English for Second Language (ESL) country (Balgoa, 2019) with 87% high literacy rates and good English speaking ability.

Several studies confirm Filipino teachers' diverse experiences in teaching English in ENL/ESL/EFL contexts. They range from Abayan et al.

investigations of the Filipino teachers' experiences in handling various language education programs in diverse cultural and linguistic settings (Cabiladas, 2023; Reyes et al., 2020; Bautista, 2020; Pontillas, 2021; Lemana, 2022) to lived experiences focusing on the benefits and challenges or pitfalls in language teaching (Ulla, 2019), and students' perceived competence of the Filipino teachers' performance (Ozaki, 2022). Although the studies showcased the Filipino teachers' experiences in teaching across the three linguistic contexts identified by Kachru (1992), the question of how Filipino teachers utilize the English varieties in teaching across the three linguistic contexts still needs to be solved.

Since most Filipino teachers nowadays are seeking opportunities to teach abroad, taking with them their own nativized and distinct variation of English, which they impart to their learners either directly or indirectly during language learners instructions, the researchers would like to know whether the English variety used by these Filipino teachers will influence the acquisition of the language or the teachers themselves will be influenced by the English variety that the students in ENL, EFL, ESL classes speak. Furthermore, it would be interesting to learn how the teachers' use of diverse English language skills in their classes affects the students and the teaching methods and goals. This investigation is carried out based on this assumption.

Research Questions

This study aims to look into Filipino teachers' experiences and perceptions when teaching English in ENL, ESL, and EFL countries. It solely covers those that discuss how teachers employ their range of English language skills in the classroom as part of their pedagogical tactics. Hence, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the teachers' experiences in terms of the use of English varieties in teaching students belonging to:
 - 1.1. English as a Native Language (ENL) Countries;
 - 1.2. English as a Second Language (ESL) Countries; and
 - 1.3. English as a Foreign Language (EFL) Countries?
2. What are the perceptions of Filipino teachers on the use of English varieties in teaching in ENL/ESL/EFL countries?

Literature Review

English language teaching (ELT) and English language education (ELE) greatly aid the global spread of English. ELT has become a global industry due to the rising demand for English proficiency worldwide (Rose et al., 2021). According to Wong and Dhubyeh-Jhaveri (2015), the most well-known model for the spread of English is Kachru's (1992) English Circles model.

The study employed Kachru's concentric circle model as the foundation for the participant's understanding of the different variations of English. The "Three-Circles Model" developed by Kachru, which distinguished three categories or groupings of English speakers according to their speech patterns, serves as the foundation for this study. He makes a distinction between countries that are "inner," "outer," and "expanding" circles. The nations that use English as their native language—the United States, the United Kingdom, Canada, Australia, and New Zealand—are called the "Inner Circle." The "Outer Circle," comprising Ghana, India, Kenya, Malaysia, Nigeria, Pakistan, Philippines, Singapore, Sri Lanka, Tanzania, and Zambia, comprises nations where English is commonly spoken as a second language and their native tongues. English is used as a foreign language in 'Expanding Circle' countries such as China, Egypt, Israel, Japan, Korea, Nepal, Saudi Arabia, Taiwan, USSR, and Zimbabwe (Wong & Dubey-Jhaveri, 2015; Jenkins, 2015; Al-Mutairi, 2020).

Speaking English as a second language (ESL) means speaking English in many formerly colonized areas. Speaking English as a foreign language (EFL) means speaking English in countries where it is used sparingly or never. The inner circle refers to those speaking English as a native language (ENL) group where, historically, English is the first language to be spoken. This research is being undertaken to uncover the experiences and perceptions of Filipino teachers regarding the many forms of English included in Kachru's circles: Inner Circle, Outer Circle, and Expanding Circle. This investigation is being carried out because the Philippines is part of the Outer Circle, and most Filipino teachers are dispersed to teach in many parts of the world carrying their nativized variety of English.

The Philippines is included in Kachru's (1992) classification of English speakers, and its citizens are regarded as second-language English speakers. Different kinds of English arose due to the significant influence of their original languages, even though the colonization effect of English was the reason it extended to the Philippine context. As a result, they bring their distinct accents of English to the classroom, which is visible in how they speak and interact with their students. This approach is closely related to the research being done since it looks into the experiences ESL teachers have when teaching English to students in different groups inside Kachru's concentric circles. It also relates to the planned study because it discusses how teachers' English language competency impacts children. In this instance, the main concern of this study is the effect of teachers' use of different varieties of English on their learners in ENL/ESL/EFL countries.

English has adapted and found its niche and relevance to a wide variety of speakers wherever it comes into contact with other languages of the world through its widespread adoption for varied purposes in locales diverse in linguistic and cultural makeup. English has unquestionably gained recognition worldwide and developed into a truly global language. Furthermore, several scholars have studied the linguistic characteristics of Englishes, or as Kachru refers to them, "World Englishes," in light of the language's globalization. Kachru (1985) defined "World Englishes" (WE) as a word used to describe newly emerging localized or indigenous variations of

English, particularly those that have emerged in areas where the United States or the United Kingdom have been influenced. The initial goal of the study of World Englishes was to codify different forms of the language that are used in various sociolinguistic contexts around the world and to examine the ways that sociolinguistic histories, multicultural backgrounds, and functional contexts affect English usage in various parts of the world (Rose & Galloway, 2015).

There is a growing body of study on World Englishes, and many ELT scholars argue that teaching World Englishes in the classroom is essential (Matsuda, 2003). Thus, using WE in the classroom has also yielded favorable outcomes for English learners, as evidenced by the studies conducted by Chang (2014) and Tanghe (2014). These studies demonstrate that non-native speakers can enhance their speaking confidence in English. Moreover, Wetzel (2013) exemplified that she enhances linguistic diversity in an Ohio University composition class. She fosters awareness of World Englishes (WE) among her students by providing insights into language variance and encouraging them to critically examine their encounters with WE users and texts. She asserts that incorporating World English (WE) in classrooms is crucial in the United States, considering the diverse population of the country and the increasing interactions between American English speakers and WE users in both spoken and written communication. Therefore, it is argued that exposing students to WE will impact their favorable sentiments toward WE users and enhance their readiness for intercultural communication. Nevertheless, the review conducted by Ramatillah et al. (2022) found that the instruction of World Englishes (WE) is primarily in the first stage, as most English teachers and learners still favor native English dialects. Conversely, incorporating WE into English learners' studies could enhance their confidence in utilizing the English language, which correlates with the studies of Chang (2014) and Tanghe (2014).

English has been dubbed "English as an International Language (EIL)" or "English as a Lingua Franca" since it is currently thought to be the most significant language to use for communication amongst speakers of other languages. Not only does the Expanding Circle inform the uses of English abroad, but native speakers and speakers of Outer Circle English are also included. In a study by Hurtig (2007), Swedish teachers believed that British English is perceived as more formal, intellectual, rigid, and accurate than American English. For educational purposes, they prefer British English, permitting teachers to utilize this dialect for instruction. Moreover, the significance of English accents in comprehending the language's usage in communication has been greatly emphasized. Chang (2014) states that the majority of English teachers, especially those who are not native English speakers, still favor British or American English as the standard for English communication.

Quirk (1990) discussed Englishes in various contexts, particularly in the Outer-Circle countries. He suggested these English variations were interference varieties and advised English teachers to emphasize native norms and native-like performance. He also emphasized the importance of maintaining a single standard for English usage in both Inner Circle and non-Inner Circle countries. Additionally, he made the point that to control the use of English in various situations; there needs to be a uniform standard of usage for both spoken and written English. He suggested this because he hoped that English would split into many incomprehensible varieties and retain its ability for cross-border communication. However, Kachru (1985) thought that accepting a range of norms would not result in a lack of understandability among various English language users. Widdowson (1994) agreed with Kachru, pointing out that many bilingual English language users learn the language in educational settings, which place a premium on a specific standard and frequently guarantee certain unifying forms. According to Widdowson (2012), English is no longer exclusive to native English speakers but is now accessible to anyone who utilizes it.

In Southeast Asia, Kirkpatrick (2008) exemplified that people in ASEAN speak several dialects of English. Additionally, it has been discovered that new English dialects exist worldwide, particularly in Southeast Asia (Mesthrie & Bhatt, 2008). This indicates that individuals in ASEAN use English dialects. English is thought to have been modified from native norm to local norm or variations norm due to English localization (Kachru & Nelson, 2006) to meet the needs of communicating between native and non-native English speakers. Kirkpatrick (2010) states that new English dialects have emerged in ASEAN nations and are utilized by non-native speakers with distinct identities in particular or local contexts. Since English is the working language of the ASEAN Community, founded in 2015, he stated that recently, regarding English variants, using English as a lingua franca has become a critical issue for ASEAN. English as a lingua franca communication pertains to "interactions between members of two or more different lingua cultures in English, for none of whom English is the mother tongue." Kirkpatrick (2008) emphasized several variations of English used as the lingua franca in ASEAN. Jindapitak and Teo (2013) found that participants' perceptions of non-native varieties of English aligned with the concept of English as a Lingua Franca, emphasizing the importance of including World English in language classrooms. This inclusion aims to raise awareness about the existence of different English varieties and promote effective communication among non-native speakers.

Despite the differences, English is viewed as an international language frequently used to communicate. As a result, educators adapt to the cultural backgrounds of their learners and are cognizant of the many English dialects. They could comprehend, accept, and be exposed to various English dialects and varieties in this way. This is made clear by McKay (2018), who claims that because English can provide access to commerce, technology, travel, science, academic study, research, and economic success, it is "infused with social and political significance." The world of English language teaching is dominated by an "innovative, often predatory culture of integrated skills located in the private sector or commercially run language centers in universities and colleges in Britain, Australasia and North America (BANA)" (or abroad through organizations like the British Council), which instructs others on what English to teach and learn in addition to how to teach it (Holliday, 2008). Additionally, English language teaching is referred to by Gray (2010) as "a service industry," in which instructors are "technicians trained solely to develop language skills," and students are clients.

Any variant of English native to the Philippines, including those used by the media and the vast majority of educated Filipinos, is referred to as Philippine English (similar to or related to American English). One of the nation's two official languages, along with Filipino (Tagalog), English is taught in schools. With its roots in English in the Philippines, a national variation known as Philippine English has undergone enormous evolution and is one of the fastest-developing languages in the postcolonial world. The origins of the English spoken by a significant portion of the Filipino populace may be traced back to the United States, when public education was introduced and was primarily taught in English. This time frame was widely recognized as starting with the Thomasites' entrance right after the Philippine Revolution in the late 19th century and lasting until early 1900.

Based on the World Englishes framework developed by renowned linguist Braj Kachru, a specific type of English known as Philippine English is now a recognized variety with its own unique lexical, phonological, and grammatical features (with significant variations across socioeconomic groups and levels of education being predictors of English proficiency in the Philippines). Bautista (2003) highlights that in the Philippines, the study of English is approached from the perspective of interference, as there are insufficient efforts to achieve the standard of American English. Research on phonology has shown that the schwa sound is not present. Instead, [a] is substituted for [ae], [] for [o], [I] for [i], and [e] for [e]. Additionally, [s] is substituted for [z], [s] for [z], [t] for [θ], [d] for [ð], [p] for [f], and [b] for [v]. Consonant clusters at the end of words are simplified, and the rhythm of speech is syllable-timed rather than stress-timed. According to Kachru and Nelson (2009), it was just a matter of time until the English language became sufficiently indigenized in Philippine society to set itself apart from English variations spoken in the United States, the United Kingdom, or other countries.

The specific goal of this study is to ascertain how Filipino teachers' nativized English language variety influences the English instruction they provide to their students in the three groups. Research indicates that when learners of a language are taught a nativized form of the language, they frequently acquire several variations of it. The study's findings and the relevant literature discussed in this paper are closely related to the study since they offer extensive background knowledge on the experiences and perceptions of Filipino teachers working abroad. This study focuses on the pedagogical approaches teachers utilize in the classroom to use a variety of English in teaching students in ENL, EFL, and ESL countries.

Methodology

The Qualitative Approach is utilized in this linguistic research to gather and analyze data. Given that the study focuses on the experiences and perceptions that Filipino teachers have when teaching English in ENL, ESL, and EFL countries, the researcher employs case study, a type of research methodology that is intended to produce a comprehensive, multidimensional understanding of a complicated problem within its actual setting also referred to as a "bounded system" (for a single case) or "multiple bounded systems" (for several cases) (Tashakkori & Creswell, 2007). Three Filipino female teachers were chosen as participants using purposive sampling were selected according to the following criteria: Filipino female teachers who are teaching English to middle/junior high school in ENL, ESL, and EFL countries only, ages ranged from 25-45, with Masters degree related to their field of teaching, and has taught English for more than two years. Pseudonyms were used to obscure the names of the individuals, and their linked schools were not disclosed for security and privacy reasons. The names Teacher Jane, Teacher Mary, and Teacher Rose were assigned to them. The statements and responses of the study participants were only included, and the researchers' views, practices, and personal experiences were excluded from the study. Despite being English teachers, none of the researchers have prior experience teaching ENL and EFL students in the language. After that, it is guaranteed that their opinions, experiences, and ideas regarding the study were not incorporated into the data analysis. Moreover, instruments, including focus group discussions (FGD), were used to collect data during group discussions, informal interviews, and Google form-based questionnaires to extract relevant information about the participants. Comparisons between the outcomes of the Focus Group Discussion, the information from the individual interviews, and the data from the questionnaires were used to triangulate the data. The research data for this study were gathered through observation, interviews, analysis, and interpretation, and thematic analysis was employed to examine the data. As Creswell (2013) outlined, the steps of data analysis are as follows: 1. Organizing and Preparing the Data for Analysis; 2. Reading and Looking at All Data ; 3. Coding the Data; 4. Using the Coding process to Generate a description of the people, Setting, or Categories/Themes for Analysis; 5. Advancing How the Description and Themes will be Represented in the Qualitative Narrative; and 6—interpreting the Findings or Results.

Results and Discussion

The tables below reveals the teachers' experiences in terms of the use of English varieties in teaching students belonging to English as a Native Language (ENL) Countries, English as Foreign Language (EFL), and English as a Second Language (ESL).

Table 1. *Filipino Teachers' Use of English Varieties in Various Context*

Linguistic Groups	Sample Extracts	Themes
ENL	"It's content relevant that's why I use American English. I can integrate Filipino English or an informal conversation but for content, for the relevance of my content it needs to be American English.... So again I would like to emphasize it's more about the relevance of content in order for them to be prepared for the Florida Standards Assessments (FSA)." – Teacher Jane	American English as a Primary Variety for Teaching
	"..So those are the American English that I have to teach, that we have to teach. I have to be very specific with it because those are the choice of words that they need to know as they are going to do their FSA." – Teacher Jane	
	"..I integrate, like "we say this but in America you say this".. So if you happen to come or go to the Philippines to visit, don't use those words because people might misinterpret you. So that is the time that I can insert Filipino English... I can integrate Filipino English or an informal conversation." – Teacher Jane	Use of Philippine English Variety for Students' Awareness
	"I use American English so that they will be prepared as they are going to encounter those words when they're taking FSA. It's content relevant, that's why I use American English... There are words that I need to use for them to make it as a tool for them to understand their questions and what is being asked... - Teacher Jane	Use of Language Variety for Specific Purpose
ESL	"...it's more effective to use Philippine English for my students because they can relate; they can understand much better compared to American English; they can express themselves..." – Teacher Mary	Philippine English as Primary English Variety for Teaching
	"...it should be the Standard American English for the students to be exposed to...for them to really know what's the standard...what should be, ought to be and the correctness of the language..." -Teacher Mary	Awareness of other varieties
	"...The thing is most of the time I use Philippine English because students have this problem with vocabulary and when we try to expose them like in American English, they have this difficulty. But, then I use American English somehow... most of the time actually they listen... but it's more on the use of Philippine English really. They can connect easily, and they can understand..." – Teacher Mary	Alternating English Language Varieties
EFL	"Yes, teach them expressions. What I did was read and write the expressions in English and Pazathai (Thai Language). "...Yes, I have to translate it to Thai language whenever I teach them expressions because if you teach them using pure English, they don't understand..." – Teacher Rose	Thai English as a Primary Variety for teaching
	"..I'm using a Filipino Variety of English. I use the simplest form. (SIMPLIFIED) We don't use flowery words because they really can't understand. Sometimes I crack jokes but they don't understand..". "..I used Philippine English because its easier not just for me but for my students to understand. When you use British, they find it hard to understand it, maybe because of the accent. And because I don't want to make things complicated.." – Teacher Rose	Use of Language Variety for Specific Purposes
	"...I used mixed varieties like American English, Philippine English and Thai English..." – Teacher Rose	Use of Alternate Varieties

Based on the ENL sample extracts, American English is the primary language teaching variety in a nation where English is spoken as a native language (ENL). Aside from American English being the language of instruction in the ENL classroom, it is also the language spoken by most students in school, in their neighborhood, and at home. Therefore, to support efficient language instruction, language teachers working in ENL classrooms see the necessity to not only be able to speak American English but also to speak the English variety as a native speaker speaks it. Given that the children speak it, Teacher Jane sees benefits in using American English. She finds it easy to communicate with her students in this language since American English is the language that is most commonly spoken in the community and at school.

Teacher Jane believes that having the students speak various languages encourages them to participate more actively in class discussions. Students find it easy to express themselves in American English because they speak their mother tongue, which makes learning easier. American English is also more appropriate for the material being taught in the classroom.

"It is content-relevant, and that is why I use American English. I can integrate Filipino English or an informal conversation, but for the relevance of my content, it needs to be American English.... So again, I would like to emphasize that it is more about the relevance of content for them to be prepared for the Florida Standards Assessments (FSA)."

"..So those are the American English that I have to teach, that we have to teach. I have to be very specific with it because those are the

choice of words that they need to know as they are going to do their FSA."

According to Rezaei et al. (2019), one motivation for students to emphasize studying standard English types is to successfully pass standardized English tests, such as the International English Language Testing System (IELTS). Educators in ENL classrooms must be able to provide the necessary English variety of instruction in a setting where English is both the medium of instruction and the native tongue. However, this presents a significant problem and calls for adaptation for ESL teachers like Jane. However, as a Filipino teacher, she struggled and needed help adapting to a new language setting. Teacher Jane first tried to employ her deeply ingrained Philippine English variety, applying its grammatical characteristics to American English to adapt it to the new English variety.

"I can't take away the Filipino English. I mean, that's part of me, but I realized, oh, so what I learned in the Philippines is far different from here."

As a non-native English speaker, she found it challenging to meet the expectations because she is not a native English speaker. Her exposure to a new English variety in the classroom presented several difficulties and problems with comprehension. She carries a lot of background knowledge about the English variety she speaks, which significantly impacts how she speaks because she was raised speaking the Philippine English variety when she was a teacher there. She found the new linguistic diversity unsettling and typically needed help understanding what the students were saying. Additionally, her pupils cannot comprehend the words and idioms she employs when speaking. There are also times when Teacher Jane finds it challenging to understand what her students are saying.

"...Every time I talk to them, they do not understand me. It is like what I mean.... if I am going to use Filipino English, they will not understand the questions they will ask."

"They love to use phrasal verbs... They would say what are these things or words that are not the words we do not usually use? It took me a fraction of a second to understand... There would be times that I do not know how to respond."

She worked very hard to master the American English variation the pupils speak so that they could execute it correctly. She made numerous observations regarding the language use of both native speakers and students. She practiced making her speech seem more like the pupils' English, examined whether her learning was correct, and asked many questions.

"I need to make sure to integrate their Daily American English choice of words for them to understand me...there are things that I learned from the best teachers in the classroom, or just like conference..."

Teacher Jane also had to change a lot of her previous knowledge because she was accustomed to a different sort of English, such as American English vocabulary, in place of the Philippine English vocabulary she carried with her.

"... There are things I need to alter, like specific words, because they do not usually use formal English here in America. It is always informal English... I have to change my choice of words so that they can easily understand me."

"...They do not understand, so I need to alter how I say things because it is easier... when you come here, you have to use American English for them to understand you primarily."

"I think vocabulary but in their context. Vocabulary in the context of their community is not more about being formal vocabulary; it is more about the slang words and the informal words that I need to know in order for me to relate to my students."

Due to the difficulties and comprehension concerns she encountered, she had to make significant changes to adapt to the American English variety used in her nation of employment. Teacher Jane said that she had to speak and sound like the pupils in order for them to comprehend her. She experimented with various methods to acquire and adapt to the new language, including reading, speaking, and practicing a lot.

"...because it is easier.. easier for me to talk to my kids.. to build rapport with them when I sound like them. .. When the students cannot understand), I corrected my choice of words to make it sound American to them..... When the students cannot understand, I correct my choice of words, which I think would make it sound American to them."

Indeed, teaching in an ENL setting while adhering to the American English variety necessitates numerous adaptations in phonology, morphology, syntax, lexicon, grammatical characteristics, and prosodic qualities of the language. These are a few fundamental preparations that English teachers must have to ensure that their work meets expectations and that teaching language becomes a fulfilling and gratifying experience.

English is not the first language spoken in the Philippines, where teacher Jane is from (ESL). Due to her linguistic background, she used Philippine English when teaching in the English Language Arts class. Teacher Jane thus employed the Philippine English variation in addition to the American English variety in the classroom. However, she stressed that she only used this variety in casual conversations, mainly when she wanted to teach her students about her language and culture. For example, she would explain to them how specific terms and expressions from their language are said or stated in Philippine English. Even in language groups where English is spoken natively, there is evidence of the usage of other language variations. In some places, it is stated that different linguistic cultures interact with one another to produce new kinds. It is inevitable for a Filipino teacher working in a nation where American English is spoken to employ the instructor's native English dialect. It is important to note that, frequently, teachers only use Philippine

English when they wish to introduce their students to their native tongue in order to blend cultures. Speaking Philippine English to the teacher is like giving a little taste of her culture through her language. This underscores Cook's (2007) research, which suggests that non-native English-speaking educators, such as those from the Philippines, possess an advantage in connecting with learners due to their proficiency in the local language.

Additionally, they tend to exhibit greater empathy towards language learners, as they can relate to their challenges. Furthermore, Hayes (2009) contributes to this argument by highlighting those non-native teachers, like those from the Philippines, may lack native speaker status but excel in situational competence. For instance, as observed in a study cited here, a respondent was not a native American or even a native English speaker by birth yet demonstrated a profound understanding of English culture surpassing that of locals. This suggests that non-native English-speaking teachers, such as those from the Philippines, often share similar cultural and ethnic backgrounds with their students while also possessing a nuanced understanding of both English-speaking countries' cultures and their own.

Using a specific English variety for English language instruction is determined by its primary objective. In an ENL nation like Florida, the main goal of the English Language Arts curriculum is to impart the knowledge and abilities needed to pass the Florida Standards Assessments (FSA), a statewide test. These standardized tests assess students' higher-order thinking abilities and progress toward Florida's state-established curricular standards. Students in grades 3 through 10 complete the English Language Arts Freestyle Assessment. The organization where Teacher Jane works mandates using the American English variety when teaching in an ENL school in Florida. Instructors believe that using this variation will help to guarantee that pupils acquire the particular knowledge and skills that will aid them in taking tests. The students in Teacher Jane's English Language Arts (ELA) class learn terminology and test-taking strategies they might face on the exam. Since the American language variant is used in the test, it is imperative to be used in instruction. In Teacher Jane's words:

"We are called English Language Arts teachers instead of English teachers... we focus more on building their skills on viewing and treating test questions to prepare them for FSA or the statewide assessment. This entails emphasizing prior knowledge and specific target content-related areas to analyze questions. Our main job is to unpack the standards and deliver specific contents to make it easier for them to identify and comprehend...."

American English is preferred as the primary language for instruction because it serves the unique goal of exposing pupils to and preparing them for exams. According to Teacher Jane, the purpose of using American English in the classroom is primarily to help the pupils learn the material and prepare for the statewide exams. As a result, Jane teaches the precise vocabulary or terms in her English language. The American English variety is purposefully used in language instruction when teaching in an ENL context. The FSA's vocabulary and other vital materials are written in American English, so they must employ this variant. Therefore, the teacher's use of any other English variety, including her Filipino English variety, would be pointless. However, Philippine English is a necessary language variety to utilize while teaching in a nation where English is used as a second language. Because the students are not native English speakers and speak their local tongue more frequently, the main goal of using Philippine English in the classroom is to help them understand the material and find it more straightforward to relate to.

Teacher Mary stresses that she must use Philippine English when speaking with her students since it is a form of the language to which they can more easily relate, be exposed to, and feel free to express themselves. In order to help her pupils who are having trouble understanding the lessons and participating in the actual discussion, an ESL teacher considers the need to change from her native English language variety and makes the necessary adaptations.

In addition to Philippine English, Teacher Mary ensures that the pupils are exposed to other variations of the language. She reveals that it is important for English teachers to adopt the American English variety when teaching because it is considered the norm and must be discussed in discussions or any kind of discourse. The standard diversity and linguistic quality must be ingrained in the learners.

"...it should be the Standard American English for the students to be exposed to...for them to know what is the standard...what should be, ought to be and the correctness, of the language..."

The usage and incorporation of other varieties—claimed to be visible in the ESL context of language instruction—become apparent. This claim is also supported by Hamid and Baldauf (2013), who found that teachers can make learners cognizant of the existing variations of English in the world. At the same time, teachers should elaborate on the features of the language differences and their implications. Though some parts of Standard English, such as semantics and syntax, will be taught in the classroom, learners are still equipped with learning avenues to learn about other varieties. They can choose to discover them more outside the classroom for actual dealings.

Because the English spoken in the Philippines is based on American English, using American English is essential in an ESL nation. Americans' long occupation of the Philippines has influenced the linguistic diversity of the Filipino people. Because of these factors, Filipinos speak separate dialects from which the term "Philippine English" originated.

In an ESL classroom, Filipino is the primary language utilized for teaching and learning, stimulating students' interest and motivation. This allows kids to understand the lesson's background while allowing them to express their opinions. Nevertheless, Teacher Mary also

switches from using Philippine English to American English, ensuring that her students acquire the standard language, particularly vocabulary, syntax, morphology, and phonology. She is taking this action because she wants her students to be completely prepared to use the standard variety of English in the future, as it will benefit their personal and professional development.

"...Most of the time, I use Philippine English because students have this problem with vocabulary, and when we try to expose them, like in American English, they have this difficulty. But, then I use American English somehow... most of the time, they listen... but it is more on the use of Philippine English. They can connect easily, and they can understand..."

Teacher Mary's approach is supported by insights from Lee et al. (2015) study, which emphasizes the effectiveness of a bilingual approach in language instruction. While acknowledging the necessity for students to master standard English, it is essential to note that comprehension forms the foundation of language acquisition. Thus, teaching primarily in Philippine English facilitates better understanding among students, enabling them to connect more easily with the material. Although Teacher Mary occasionally introduces American English, she finds that students encounter difficulties with vocabulary when solely exposed to it. This reaffirms the importance of using a medium familiar to students for effective language learning.

However, the Philippine educational system has made it policy to permit pupils to utilize their mother tongue to maximize their learning potential. Teacher Mary is the one who makes adjustments to help her students become more proficient and comprehend the teaching process. She carefully considers how to suit the needs of her students by using a variety of English language expressions and alternative ways of using a particular language. As said by Teacher Mary:

"...if they do not understand even when we try to use it in Philippine English, somehow, we need to 50% Filipino and 50% English... I need to resort to Bisaya..."

The only reason American English is preferred is to introduce pupils to several dialects and help them get familiar with the mainstream one, which is essential for language growth and career ladder preparation. According to Teacher Mary, the teacher has the right to progressively close the knowledge gap regarding the subject matter and its many discourses by utilizing the various language types in a varied way. On the other hand, English is frequently employed as a key to open doors of communication and understanding among individuals in different countries, despite its claims to be an international or universal language. Furthermore, English is essential to fulfilling its many responsibilities as the official language, the medium of teaching, a required subject, and a lingua franca. International acceptance of English's use as a communication tool has led to its rapid assimilation into the curriculum for Thai students pursuing a senior high school degree.

Thailand is considered a nation of the expanding circle (EC) in Kachru's Concentric Circle. Thai students must be aware of the various forms of English because it has become a working language in the Asian community. English is seen as an essential subject to the language education system in Thailand because it serves as a gatekeeping mechanism. Since pupils begin attending school at a young age, it is learned. From elementary school through the university level, English is a required subject. To help students become more aware of how Thai linguistic terms are translated, Teacher Rose emphasizes the importance of using English reading materials written by Thai authors. She says students can compare the English usage in these translated texts with the original Thai variety. Similarly, Teacher Rose also brought attention to one of the most prevalent language problems associated with students' learning: their inadequate English ability.

Furthermore, the nation's and its citizens' growth depends on teaching and learning the English language. Furthermore, English is not frequently spoken or utilized in Thailand, making English language teaching one of the most sought-after careers for native and non-native English speakers. English is not utilized as a medium of instruction in colleges or universities. This explains why some Thai students find it challenging to communicate in the language, even though they have been exposed to the English language since elementary school.

"...I am so resourceful because we need that here in Thailand, especially in teaching the students here because they have zero knowledge about English. So every time you teach them, you should have the PowerPoint or visual presentation because they cannot understand..."

Teacher Rose's approach receives strong support from Amjah (2014), who acknowledges the challenges teachers face when teaching English to Thai students who lack interest in learning the language. Teachers must employ effective teaching strategies to overcome this hurdle and make language learning engaging and enjoyable. These strategies encompass information and communication technology (ICT), games, interactive activities, and other engaging materials tailored for language instruction. By incorporating these elements into their teaching practices, teachers can stimulate and enhance students' interest and motivation to learn English.

Teacher Rose also mentioned that she has been studying the local tongue to build rapport with her students and foster mutual understanding. As said by her:

"...Yes, ma'am. Sometimes I speak Thai to them. Its also advantage to me when I speak Thai so that they can really understand..."

Teacher Rose typically has to play a vital role in the classroom to instill in her students the significance of studying the English language when they are uninterested. As a Filipino English teacher in Thailand, Teacher Rose has experience instructing students in English as

a foreign language because she was trained to do so in her native Philippines. Moreover, she stated that:

"... how to communicate and how to let the students understand what you are teaching. As a teacher, my primary goal is to teach them and let them learn. I want them to learn something from me when they go to university..."

As she clarified, teachers were likely to be essential mediators between language ideology, language theory, and language policy as they were in charge of choosing the textbooks, delivering the courses, creating the assessments, and assessing students' language proficiency. In short, Kurland and Hassan (2015) provide strong support for Teacher Rose's claims.

It was noted that teaching English in an EFL context involves using alternate varieties. "The use of other English varieties in language teaching" is what we mean when we refer to other varieties. Teacher Rose said she uses many types to help her students learn languages. She claimed to "mix up" her use of American, Filipino, and Thai English variations when she needed to clarify meanings for her students who were having trouble understanding certain words. While teaching English to Thai pupils, Teacher Rose makes sense of assignments, obligations, and free time in three languages every day. Her time spent with her Thai students revealed how fluidly and gracefully they speak English.

English teachers like Teacher Rose firmly believe that by encouraging discussions of content in multiple languages, describing new vocabulary to her Thai students, and creating cross-linguistic connections when teaching English, they can assist Thai students in realizing the excellent linguistic resources at their disposal and starting to use them for academic success. She also maintains that using various languages helps kids expand their linguistic repertoire and gives families and communities new perspectives, making them partners in her students' literacy growth. The domains of education, family, and community are connected through translanguaging. One tool for creating meaning is language. O. According to García (2009), employing different varieties implies that linguistic resources—knowing several languages and dialects—are a component of a single language system that a person utilizes to make sense of the world and achieve objectives. Students can strengthen critical elements of their reading comprehension toolkits, such as summarizing and vocabulary understanding, as well as develop their multilingual proficiencies and metalinguistic awareness by using alternate varieties or flexibly moving across languages and registers of speech in conjunction with their educators (Cummins, 2007; Martin-Beltrán & Peercy, 2014). However, learning language is a continual, broad practice that a learner engages in regularly rather than something they "have." Examples of using alternative kinds and practices are code-switching, translating, language brokering, and interpreting amongst people from different cultural and linguistic backgrounds. The claims made by Teacher Rose are corroborated by Otheguy et al. (2015), who state that employing translanguaging strategies in the classroom allows teachers to understand better how a student's culture and language skills interact with them and serves as an efficient teaching method for enhancing their language proficiency.

Further discussion above shows similarities and differences in their practices on the use of language varieties employed in teaching across the three concentric circles of language contexts. One notable observation is that each language context has a specific and distinct practice regarding the primary language variety for instruction. The most significant observation that could be noted is that all three linguistic groups consider American English as the primary reference for the standard variety of English Language Teaching.

Table 2. Teachers' Perceptions on the English Variety for Teaching

Extracted Utterances	Themes
<i>"Language is not effective if your purpose is to teach, it's not effective if you are using a different variety of English. You need to adjust to their needs, not yours... it's not functional (use of Philippine English) . I think it's functional when they belong or they have Filipino peers. But no, I don't think so because their Filipino peers grew up here, so it doesn't make sense either. So unless they are gonna go to the Philippines, that would be functional." - Teacher Jane</i>	Functionality
<i>"it's useless if you're if I'm using Filipino English and they don't understand me so what's the point of it, you have to use their language American English language so it's easier for you to comprehend" -Teacher Jane</i>	Proximity to Dominant Variety
<i>" I also use Philippine English in order that my students will be aware of the Philippine culture. But I only use if I want to hang out with my kids ... I want to share with them my culture through my language." -Teacher Jane</i> <i>"...For me, personally I would really want to include the standard American English and other varieties for them... because we are looking into the future... we want them to really maximize their exposure... and preparing them to be global citizens..." - Teacher Mary</i>	Inclusion and Awareness
<i>"I try to use American English because students understand it.... I use Philippine English, they don't understand me... I try my best to speak and sound like them so that they will understand what I am saying." - Teacher Jane</i> <i>"Just use American English because they can easily understand only if I already taught that word. If I introduce a new word, I used American English. It's better to use the standard English so that students were not get confuse. It's my fault that I used mixed varieties in teaching that's why my students got confused. That's why I would advise for those new teachers to use one variety.-Teacher Rose</i>	Propensity for Comprehension

Table 2 reflects the generalization about the teachers' perspectives of the use of English varieties in teaching, which result from their varied experiences with suitable English varieties in the classroom. These perceptions reflect the instructors' perceived knowledge and beliefs on the use of English variations in English language instruction in their various work settings.

Choosing which English variety to utilize for teaching functionality is one of the main factors. The term "functionality" describes the attribute or state of being useful. Therefore, the selection of an English variety is determined by its primary purpose for use.

The main goal of instruction in the ENL environment is for students to pass competitive exams. Thus, students must employ a variety of suitable English when taking examinations to pass the abovementioned examinations.

The significance of various English proficiency tests, such as the Michigan English Language Assessment Battery (MELAB), Test of English as a Foreign Language (TOEFL), and International English Language Testing System (IELTS), is closely tied to the primary goal of instruction in English as a New Language (ENL) environments: preparing students for success in competitive exams. These exams are crucial for evaluating learners' language skills globally and are widely recognized assessments for non-native English speakers. MELAB, recognized explicitly as an alternative to TOEFL in multiple educational institutions across the USA, Canada, and the United Kingdom, covers composition writing, listening comprehension, and multiple-choice tests, with speaking optional. Conversely, TOEFL and IELTS evaluate proficiency in all four essential language skills: reading, writing, listening, and speaking (Karpinski, 2018).

Given the imperative nature of passing these competitive exams, students must utilize the appropriate English variety during these assessments to enhance their chances of success. These exams reveal learners' proficiency levels and serve as benchmarks for achieving academic and professional goals. Therefore, instructors in ENL environments must prioritize equipping students with the necessary language skills to excel in these examinations, aligning with the overarching goal of preparing students for success in competitive exams.

The main goal of employing their owl language variations in ESL and EFL environments is to grasp better the concepts taught in class. The primary goal of language teaching must be achieved because students will need help understanding concepts presented in the English variety considered standard English by the teacher. Therefore, students must use their American English in the context of the Philippines and their Thai English in the context of Thailand.

The American English variety must be used extensively while teaching English in an ENL setting. Therefore, the proximity of the language variation to the dominant language is essential for Filipino teachers of English to guarantee that the variety they use in the classroom is close to the language that most students speak and understand. If the instructor believes that her English variety is confusing the kids and creating problems for her, she may need to make the appropriate adjustments. Making much effort to acquire and use the language pays off.

Thus, it would also be necessary to consider the majority language spoken in a particular language group when selecting appropriate English varieties for instruction. Hence, a teacher must speak a variation that matches the target language variety to teach a particular variety effectively. "State of being near or close approximate to the target language" defines language proximity. Therefore, to improve comprehension and learning, a teacher using American English must speak the language in a manner akin to that of native speakers.

Several English dialects were deemed necessary for inclusion and awareness in the ENL/ESL/EFL settings of English language teaching techniques. The necessity to incorporate the varieties selected by the teachers was implemented for specific reasons, even though it was noted that the use of English variety is strongly associated with the language backgrounds of the learners. In order to help students in ENL and EFL countries become more aware of other cultures, teachers adapt their variation of English. However, to acquaint pupils with the current standard variety of English, American English variety is necessary in ESL and EFL countries.

Incorporating the various English dialects into the teaching and learning process undoubtedly raised students' awareness of their existence and the differences between them, but more importantly, it encouraged them to respect the cultures of others and to consider things from a different angle. Having said that, because English is regarded as the universal language, educators should expose their students to the relationship between languages, broaden their horizons, and help them comprehend the dialectal variations that serve as the foundation for the various English dialects that have developed and are spoken around the globe.

Bećirović (2012) stresses the importance of multiculturalism and diversity in schools, advocating for teachers to nurture and accept these diversities to foster inclusion. This emphasis on embracing cultural differences aligns with the claim that incorporating various English dialects into the teaching and learning process can raise students' awareness of linguistic diversity and encourage respect for different cultures.

By exposing students to the relationship between languages and broadening their understanding of dialectal variations, educators can help students comprehend the foundation of various English dialects spoken worldwide. This approach enhances students' language proficiency and promotes intercultural understanding and respect, ultimately contributing to a more inclusive and harmonious classroom environment.

The teachers' preference for a language that may improve students' comprehension, knowledge, and learning is also reflected in the

English variety they choose to teach. Even though the majority of them had trouble comprehending the various types of English spoken in class, the teachers decided to modify the English variety to help the pupils understand it better.

Students in the ENL environment widely use American English since it is the language they speak at home, school, and in the community. The teacher made the required change by ensuring she was fluent and proficient in speaking the language. However, she was unable to utilize her own English variety because it did not relate to the students or the objectives of the English Language sessions.

Teaching English as a foreign language in Thailand differs from teaching English as a second language. Teacher Rose's experience teaching in Thailand provided her with valuable teaching insights. Her primary goal as an English instructor is to develop the most efficient teaching methods for her Thai students. She still preferred American English when she spoke and wrote, as well as when she taught and used English in the classroom in terms of pronunciation, vocabulary, and English communication expressions, even though, as an English teacher, she would tend to embrace the legitimacy of World Englishes (WE), or English varieties, and Thai English, especially in terms of different linguistic variations and the use of Thai English (along with inner circle Englishes) in international communication.

The emphasis on focusing on learning outcomes regardless of individual backgrounds, as highlighted by Rizvić & Bećirović (2017), aligns with the approach taken by Teacher Rose in her English as a New Language (ENL) classroom. Despite teaching in Thailand, where English is learned as a foreign language, Teacher Rose recognizes the importance of adapting her teaching methods to suit Thai students' needs. She acknowledges the significance of incorporating American English, which is widely used by her students in their daily lives while embracing the legitimacy of World Englishes (WE) and Thai English.

Furthermore, Teacher Rose's commitment to creating a pleasant and inclusive multicultural classroom environment resonates with Doyle's (2006) assertion that flexibility is crucial when teaching students from diverse cultures. Teacher Rose facilitates effective communication and engagement with her students by ensuring fluency and proficiency in American English, contributing to their overall learning experience. This approach enriches the classroom environment through diverse linguistic perspectives and enhances students' language proficiency and cultural awareness.

Conclusions

The study reveals that Filipino teachers in three linguistic groups, ENL, ESL, and EFL, consider American English as the primary reference for the standard variety for English Language Teaching and likewise perceive the use of these varieties for functionality or state of being useful in their classroom instructions. The English variety will vary depending on several criteria and underlying considerations. Due to their diverse national origins, teachers and pupils have varying linguistic backgrounds. They also speak different dialects of English, which are heavily impacted by their original language. For teachers and students, the decision to teach diverse English styles presented several difficulties and necessary changes. The primary objective of education is to provide students with the necessary communication skills since, in certain situations, they may be having trouble speaking orally or in writing. The degree of exposure to the language will determine the kids' proficiency in speaking it. It follows that people who are least exposed to American English are likely to find it challenging to communicate in any form of English. Therefore, language teachers need to receive training on supporting and encouraging students' self-directed learning and fostering a love of learning. For individuals who have a strong interest in learning, increasing their knowledge and study will continually improve their comprehension and production abilities.

Regardless of the teacher's linguistic background, in order to meet the needs of the students, please provide them with the opportunity to express their ideas, help them gain confidence in the language, promote holistic development, and close the learning gap; the teacher must adapt to the student's level of competence, comprehension, and choice of English language varieties. As a result, to facilitate successful instruction and accelerate learning, the teacher must show excellent care for linguistic diversity among the students and be willing to make concessions. Nonetheless, to help students grasp the idea of language diversity, enable teachers to be more adaptable, and identify linguistic variances, it is necessary to expose students to the various variations of English and use these varieties in the teaching and learning process.

The study's findings suggest that using an appropriate English variety when teaching is one of the critical factors teachers should consider when instructing students in English in ENL, ESL, or EFL contexts. The kind of variety that is used in the classroom will vary depending on the type of class that is being taught, the language variety that is spoken by most of the students, the main goal of using the language variety, and the student's comprehension and adaptability to the teacher's initial introduction and use of the language variety.

The study's findings lead to the recommendation of the following points precisely: To thoroughly understand and recognize the use of the English varieties, teachers must complete training on Philippine English and other English variations. Language instructors need to benchmark their programs to identify internal areas where teaching English and its variants could be improved. This study would persuade decision-makers to change the educational system's language policies to incorporate World English. To help the students develop personal communication skills, the teacher should offer Philippine English and other dialects in addition to American English so that the students are completely conversant in the language. Further, investigate the students' viewpoints about English instruction and learning activities.

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